

THE NATIONAL RESEARCH CENTRE FOR SCIENCE

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The French Higher Education system is composed of 74 public universities, but there are also engineering schools and RPOs that do not deliver diplomas but often help train doctoral students – such as the National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS). There are also 13 private universities recognised by the state. The gender policy implemented at universities and RPOs is set by the French Ministry of Education, Research, and Innovation (MESRI). This policy has focused on gender-based violence (GBV) since about 2015, whereas previous policies focused more on careers. Today, while equality is still an objective, GBV has become a central issue. The Conference of University Presidents has also been active on this issue for at least 10 years¹ and drew up the first charter in 2013.² In 2019, all universities and RPOs were required to set up help units³ that would be in charge of fighting sexual and sexist violence, training, and communication (more than 90% of the universities now have one). The ministry supports these actions financially through an annual call for proposals, which took place in 2021 and 2022. In 2020 a decree to support the reporting of harassment and violence was issued that applies to the entire civil service (therefore including public universities and RPOs).⁴ The MESRI published a guide on the reporting procedures in effect in 2020,⁵ and a general reference document on mandatory equality action plans that include GBV.⁶ No university has been sanctioned for not complying with the regulations so far, but the issue will be on the table when they undergo their evaluations every 5 years.

¹ <http://www.cpu.fr/actualite/lutte-contre-les-violences-sexuelles-et-sexistes-des-outils-a-disposition-des-etablissements/>

² http://www.cpu.fr/wp-content/uploads/2013/01/chartes_dossier_couv_239902.pdf

³ Act No. 2019-828 of 6 August 2019 on transforming the civil service.

⁴ <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000041722970/>

⁵ <https://cache.media.enseignementsup->

recherche.gouv.fr/file/Parite_et_lutte_contre_les_discriminations/06/7/vss_enquete_guide_esri_03n_1353067.pdf

⁶ http://www.cdefi.fr/files/files/20201000 - Referentiel_plan_d_action_egalite_dans_l_ESR.pdf

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The CNRS has been active on gender equality since 2001 with the creation of the Mission for the Place of Women at the CNRS (MDPF). Efforts to address GBV at the CNRS date back to 2013 with the first Circular on sexual harassment at work, followed by the HRS4R certification in 2017 which included actions on training about sexual harassment. In 2018, the CNRS Ethics Committee issued an Opinion on sexual harassment detailing what is at stake, the legal framework and providing recommendations on how to act.

The CNRS has three main policy documents that cover GBV: The Action Plan for Professional Equality 2021-2023 is a broader document on gender equality at work that addresses GBV in one of its chapters. It includes a table outlining actions, the people responsible for them, indicators, and timelines. There are two documents dedicated to combatting GBV: the new Circular on the System for Reporting Acts of Violence, Harassment and Discrimination which sets up an e-mail address and a help line and creates the position of a national referral person, and an Internal Practical Document on Sexual Harassment and Violence. The Circular is the main and most detailed document.

URLs

- › Action Plan for professional equality 2021-2023: <https://mpdf.cnrs.fr/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Plan-action-egalite-CNRS-2021-2023.pdf>
- › Circular on the System for Reporting Acts of Violence, Harassment and Discrimination: <https://www.dgdr.cnrs.fr/bo/2021/BO-avril-2021-compressed.pdf>
- › Internal Practical Document: Not publicly available.

Entry into force: All three policy documents entered into force in **2021**.

TRAINING

Both the Equality Action Plan and the Internal Practical Document set out awareness-raising training that targets diverse stakeholders to get them to recognise GBV and discrimination.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

The CNRS has been active on gender issues in the professional sphere since 2001, when it established the MDPF. It has supported gender research since the 1970s, originally alongside a very small number of other universities. The MDPF participates in or coordinates a number of EU projects.⁷ Gender research, including research on GBV, is part of CNRS's Contract of Objectives and is framed as follows: 'The question of gendered constructions and gender relations concerns all social and symbolic practices, public and private, collective and individual'. The CNRS also operates the Gender Institute,⁸ which supports research on GBV.⁹

⁷ <https://mpdf.cnrs.fr/mpdf/projets-europeens/>

⁸ <https://institut-du-genre.fr/>

⁹ <https://institut-du-genre.fr/fr/actualites-du-genre/livres/parutions-2021/article/violences-et-rapports-de-genre>

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The three policies combined cover the following **seven** forms of violence: GBV, physical violence, psychological violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, online violence. The Equality Action Plan focuses on sexual and gender-based harassment. The two other policies cover multiple forms of GBV: psychological violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, and online violence. The only differences lie in the Internal Practical Document which addresses GBV in general, and in the Circular which addresses physical violence.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The three policies combined address all **7Ps**. While all the policies address prevention, the Circular is the only policy addressing prevalence and partnership. Both the Internal Practical Document and the Circular address prosecution. Both the Equality Action Plan and the Circular address protection and provision of services. The Internal Practical Document is the only one that can be considered to deal with the P for 'policies' P as it specifically focuses on GBV.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups

The three policies combined address all three target groups, **academic staff**, **non-academic staff**, and **students**. However, the Internal Practical Document does not address any, while the Equality Action Plan focuses on the two staff groups. The Circular addresses all groups, as well as the additional group of interns working in CNRS laboratories

Vulnerable groups addressed: Yes. The three policies combined identify **all groups defined in the UniSAFE mapping except one**, early-career researchers, as groups vulnerable to GBV. The Internal Practical Document does not identify any groups, the Equality Action Plan identifies staff with temporary contracts, and the Circular identifies international students and staff, students and staff with disabilities, students and staff with migrant and ethnic minority background, LGBTQIA+ students and staff, new and expectant mothers, and other groups such as persons with political, trade union, philosophical, or religious opinions. Moreover, one of the actions in the Equality Action Plan envisions creating resources for the heads of research units/labs on how to tackle GBV. It includes a detailed section on GBV that identifies additional groups and people in off-site settings, such as scientific days, after-work parties, and field missions (especially in an environment forcing proximity and a lack of personal space such as on boats or forest camps).

Intersectionality addressed: No.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. Bystanders are addressed in two policies, the Equality Action Plan and the Circular. The Equality Action Plan emphasises the fact that bystanders should also have access to social and psychological support, while the Circular states that the procedures are for both victims/survivors and witnesses/bystanders.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. Chapter 3 of the Circular sets out relocation measures, including temporarily moving the alleged perpetrator to another service. Sanctions are not specified in the Circular because the general frame of disciplinary sanctions already exists separately.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Yes. Both the Equality Action Plan and the Circular include indicators. The Equality Action Plan refers to the number of information campaigns and training sessions and the proportion of laboratories that put GBV in their internal regulations. The Internal Practical Document refers to the indicator of having set up a help unit. The Circular refers to the numbers of reports received with or without follow-up.

Monitoring: Yes. The Circular calls for the monitoring of its own implementation. The contact person makes an annual anonymous review of the cases and the treatment they received.

Evaluation: Yes. Both the Equality Action Plan and the Circular provide for the evaluation of the policies. The Equality Action Plan is evaluated by HR with a view to its renewal or further development. The Circular calls for an evaluation of the monitoring report by the social dialogue bodies to assess the risks to which staff members are subjected. The results are published online.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Yes. The only policy to set out a step-by-step institutional procedure is the Circular. There is **one procedure for all**.

The policy defines: Who to contact, how to report or make a complaint, the investigation procedure, responsible persons or units, and outcomes.

Who to contact: There is a contact person in place and a dedicated e-mail address.

Responsible person/units: The contact person is under the direct authority of the CEO. The contact person relies on the services of the HR Department (HRD) and the Legal Affairs Department (DAJ) to perform his/her work.

How to report: A victim or bystander can send an email to the contact person via a dedicated e-mail address, which is the preferred reporting channel (they can also write to the unit director, the head of the CNRS regional office, or the MPDF). They may request that their report be recorded in a telephone interview, which will be written up as a report that they will authorise as valid. Anyone who receives a report of an incident may relay the report to the contact person under conditions that guarantee its confidentiality and only with the consent of the author of the report (a victim or a bystander), who will be informed that the report has been passed on. The reporting system guarantees the strict confidentiality of the identity of the author of the report, the persons concerned, and the facts that are the subject of the report.

The author of the report must precisely describe the facts of the incident in which they consider themselves to have been a victim or the incident they have witnessed, and should provide, if possible, information or documents (any medium) that can support the content of the report (e.g. exchanges of e-mails, a report of a complaint that was filed, a work suspension, a report documenting a work accident, etc.). A person who has witnessed an incident will also indicate the circumstances that led them to have obtained personal knowledge of it. The author of the report provides the contact details of bystanders so that they can be contacted. If the author of the report is not a French-speaking person, they can provide the contact details of a third party who can assist them. The report can also be recorded and written up in English. Any slanderous denunciation in which a person is wrongly accused while the accuser knows these accusations to be false, and which is done for the sole purpose of harming the accused is punishable by criminal as well as disciplinary sanctions.

Investigation:

1) *First review and access to services:* Reports are subject to a first review by the contact person. The purpose of this review is to assess the admissibility of the report and to verify whether the reported facts characterise one of the actions outlined in the Circular. The verification relates to the nature of the facts and the existence of justifications provided to support the report. It also helps to ensure that knowledge of the facts has been acquired personally by the complainant and that the report is made in good faith. If the facts in the report do not correspond to one of the actions specified, the contact person needs to inform the complainant of the report's inadmissibility within one month. If the content of the report lies outside the scope of the Circular, the contact person needs to direct the complainant to the appropriate services. After that the file is closed. If the report is admissible, the contact person informs the author of the report of how they will learn of the

response to their report and of the foreseeable processing times. The contact person must ensure that the author of the report agrees to have the report passed on to the authorities designated to handle the case, while respecting the confidentiality of the information communicated. The contact person must also offer the author of the report the contact information of the CNRS's legal affairs department in the event that the complainant wishes to take advantage of legal counsel, request functional protection, and/or initiate legal proceedings.

2) *Administrative investigation*: If the report is admissible, an administrative investigation is carried out. This can be conducted at different levels (regional or national) depending on the employee's position. As far as possible, investigations should be conducted by an equal number of men and women and by a representative of the employer of each of the persons concerned. If the investigation is carried out at the level of the regional delegation, it is carried out under the authority of the regional delegate. The CNRS is composed of 17 regional delegations which provide direct and local management of the laboratories and maintain links with local partners and authorities. The Human Resources Departments of the regional delegations are responsible for conducting interviews with the persons named in the report as soon as possible, starting with the author of the report, followed by the person(s) concerned, and potential witnesses. Each interviewee is reminded of the circumstances that gave rise to the investigation and will have to sign the transcript of their interview. These interviews make it possible to collect material evidence that can establish or refute the facts described in the report and to assess the context in which they took place. The purpose of the interview is also to determine the responsibility attributable to each person whom the reported facts concern. Anyone who discloses any part of the investigation, or the investigation itself, can be considered to have demonstrated the intent to harm those involved in the incident and is therefore liable to be subject to punishment.

3) *Investigation report*: A report is drawn up by the regional delegation in charge of the investigation. It summarises the facts from the initial report and the stages of the hearing phase and indicates whether or not the facts have been established. It also provides information useful for understanding the case and likely to enlighten the chairperson and CEO on what further steps to take. This report must contain an annex with all the material evidence collected during the investigation. This report is sent to the contact person, who can draw up conclusions on its basis. Throughout the investigation, the author of the report is kept informed of the progress of the investigation/case. If the reported facts concern a person who is required to play a role in the investigation conducted at the regional level or any person who holds an important hierarchical position, the investigation may be taken over by another relevant authority.

Outcomes: In view of the findings of the investigation, the CEO may, among other things, initiate disciplinary proceedings against the alleged perpetrator. The latter has the right to access all the documents on the case. The contact person is in charge of closing the case.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

***Acknowledgment**: this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Suzanne de Cheveigné in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

